

for the Study and the Integrated Treatment of Obesity at the University Hospital of Padova before and one year after metabolic/bariatric surgery. Furthermore, we evaluated the relationship between sP2X7R, anthropometric measurement, metabolic parameters and inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP), TNF- α and IL-6 before and after surgical weight loss.

Results: we observe that sP2X7R plasma levels are higher in patients with severe obesity respect to a control group from a healthy population. Interestingly, while no association was reported with metabolic parameters such as body weight, BMI and waist circumference, in the patients group we observed an indirect correlation between sP2X7R and CRP ($p < 0.001$), TNF- α ($p = 0.05$) and IL-6 ($p < 0.001$) at baseline. One year after metabolic surgery we observed the reduction of plasma concentration of sP2X7R (0.001) along with the other considered cytokines.

Conclusions: given the role of P2X7R in inflammation, our results suggest that sP2X7R could represent a novel marker of chronic low-grade inflammation further contributing to the development of obesity-associated complications.

References

- Adinolfi, E.; Giuliani, A.L.; De Marchi, E.; Pegoraro, A.; Orioli, E.; Di Virgilio, F. The P2X7 receptor: A main player in inflammation. *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 2018, 151, 234–244.
- Di Vincenzo A, Granzotto M, Crescenzi M, Vettor R, Rossato M. Non-aromatizable androgens modulate the lipopolysaccharide induced expression of the P2X7 receptor in human adipocytes. *Front Pharmacol.* 2023 23;14:1251035.
- Giuliani, A.L.; Berchan, M.; Sanz, J.M.; Passaro, A.; Pizzicotti, S.; Vultaggio-Poma, V.; Sarti, A.C.; Di Virgilio, F. The P2X7 receptor is shed into circulation: Correlation with c-reactive protein levels. *Front. Immunol.* 2019, 10, 793.

Conflict of Interest: None to Disclose.

Funding: No funding to report with regard to this study.

GC4.074

Beyond restrictive: Sleeve Gastrectomy to Single Anastomosis Duodenoileal Bypass with Sleeve Gastrectomy as a spectrum of one single procedure

Pereira, A. M.¹; Moura, D.²; Pereira, S. S.²; Andrade, S.²; Almeida, R. F.¹; Nora, M.¹; Monteiro, M. P.²; Guimarães, M.³

¹Department of General Surgery, Centro Hospitalar de Entre o Douro e Vouga. R. Dr. Cândido Pinho 5, 4520-211 Santa Maria da Feira, Portugal

²UMIB - Unidade Multidisciplinar de Investigação Biomédica, ICBAS - Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas Abel Salazar, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal; ITR - Laboratory for Integrative and Translational Research in Population Health

³Department of General Surgery, Centro Hospitalar de Entre o Douro e Vouga. R. Dr. Cândido Pinho 5, 4520-211 Santa Maria da Feira, Portugal; UMIB - Unidade Multidisciplinar de Investigação Biomédica, ICBAS - Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas Abel Salazar, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal; ITR - Laboratory for Integrative and Translational Research in Population Health

Introduction: Different bariatric techniques are often empirically chosen for each patient, based on the severity of their obesity and metabolic dysfunction. Single-anastomosis duodeno-ileal bypass with sleeve gastrectomy (SADI-S) is restrictive/hypoabsorptive procedure recommended for patients with obesity class 3. For safety reason, SADI-S can be safely split into two stages by performing a sleeve gastrectomy (SG) first. This step-wise approach also provides an unprecedented opportunity to disentangle the weight loss mechanisms triggered by each component. In this study, we compared weight trajectories and postprandial endocrine and metabolic responses of patients with obesity class 3 submitted to SADI-S or sleeve gastrectomy (SG) as the first step of SADI-S.

Methods: Patients submitted to one-stage SADI-S ($n = 7$) or SG ($n = 7$), at a tertiary referral public academic hospital without previous abdominal surgery, underwent a liquid mixed meal tolerance test (MMTT) pre-operatively and at 3, 6, and 12 months post-operatively, to assess the fasting and post-prandial profile of glucose and pancreatic hormones.

Results: Anthropometric parameters, as well as metabolic and micro-nutrient profiles, were not significantly different between groups, neither before nor after surgery. Fasting and post-prandial glucose, insulin,

C-peptide, ghrelin, insulin secretion rate (ISR) and insulin clearance during MMTT were similar between SADI-S and SG patients. There was no lost to follow-up.

Conclusion: Glucose and pancreatic hormone profiles after one-stage SADI-S and SG were similar, supporting the surgical restrictive component as the main driver of weight loss and metabolic adaptations during the first 12 months after SADI-S. This data provides support for a surgeons' choice of a two-step SADI-S without risking the weight loss outcomes.

GC4.075

Secondary hyperparathyroidism, bone remodeling markers and lean mass after bariatric surgery

Holanda, N. C.¹; Fonseca Moura, T. G.¹; Limeira, C. C.²; Borges, H. C.²; Carvalho, N. N.¹; Montenegro, A. C.³; Bandeira, F.⁴

¹Universidade Federal da Paraíba, João Pessoa, Brazil

²Universidade Potiguar, Natal, Brazil

³Instituto de Medicina Integral Professor Fernando Figueira, Recife, Brazil

⁴Division of Endocrinology and Diabetes, Agamenon Magalhães Hospital, Universidade de Pernambuco, Recife, Brazil

Introduction: Bariatric surgery (BS) can lead to secondary hyperparathyroidism (SHPT), bone and muscle loss, and an increased risk of fractures. The mechanisms underlying the development of SHPT and sarcopenia after BS, in addition to nutrient malabsorption, are unknown.

Methods: The aim of this study was to evaluate lean mass by DXA analysis according to serum PTH and bone markers in patients who underwent Roux-en-Y gastric bypass (RYGB) or sleeve gastrectomy (SG).

Results: We studied 103 patients (90% female, 51% RYGB, 41.8 $\pm$ 6.7 years). SHPT was more prevalent in RYGB (26%, BGYR>SG), $p = 0.01$). The mean PTH was 93.4 $\pm$ 38.4 pg/ml in the SHPT (+) group. SHPT (+) group had a greater post BS interval (6.3 $\pm$ 4.4 vs 3.8 $\pm$ 3.3 years, $p = 0.001$), BMI (34.1 $\pm$ 4.3 vs 30.5 $\pm$ 5.39 kg/m², $p = 0.002$), abdominal circumference (99.9 $\pm$ 13.3 vs 94.0 $\pm$ 12.3 cm, $p = 0.038$), and lower serum calcium (8.8 $\pm$ 1.1 vs 9.2 $\pm$ 0.5, $p = 0.016$), than SHPT (-) group. Although the SHPT (+) group had higher levels of alkaline phosphatase (AF) (9.2 $\pm$ 0.5 vs 8.8 $\pm$ 1.1, $p = 0.016$) and CTX (0.620 $\pm$ 0.26 vs 0.480 $\pm$ 0.23, $p = 0.042$), the bone mineral density (BMD) were similar between the groups. SHPT (+) group had lower appendicular skeletal mass adjusted for BMI (ASM-BMI) (22.7 $\pm$ 3.3 vs 24.7 $\pm$ 3.6, $p = 0.041$), and we found an inverse correlation between ASM-BMI and PTH (r Pearson = - 0.1977, $p = 0.0325$). There were no differences in physical performance or muscle strength according to the presence of SHPT. After linear regression analysis, RYGB technique, post BS interval, higher serum CTX and lower serum calcium were independently associated with SHPT.

Conclusion: SHPT is common after BS, especially after RYGB, and is associated with decreased lean mass and increased bone turnover.

GC4.076

The role of modulation of cellular senescence in the metabolic effects of bariatric surgery

Hubáčková Štemberková, S.¹; Havrlantová, T.¹; Šimonik, I.²; Haluzík, M.³

¹Centre for Experimental Medicine, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

²St. Zdislava Hospital, Mostistě, Velke Mezirici, Czech Republic

³Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

Introduction: Bariatric surgery is the most efficient approach to the treatment of obesity, however the detailed mechanism of its positive metabolic effects beyond weight loss is still not fully understood. Cellular senescence arrests the damaged cells thus prevent further spreading of the damage. However, excessive persistence of senescent cells especially in adipose tissue can contribute to subclinical inflammation and development of type 2 diabetes and other chronic metabolic diseases. Our study explored the effects of bariatric surgery on the circulating markers of cellular senescence and the presence of senescent cells in adipose tissue before and after surgery.

Methods: 47 patients with obesity with or without type 2 diabetes mellitus undergoing bariatric surgery (sleeve gastrectomy) were included into the study. Subcutaneous (SAT) adipose tissue and fasting blood samples were collected during the surgery (V1) and 6 month after the surgery (V3). The analysis of samples included RT-qPCR (mRNA transcription in SAT) and standard biochemical methods, ELISA or Luminex for detection of hormones and other relevant parameters in plasma.

Results: Bariatric surgery reduced amount of senescent cells in adipose tissue (57% reduction) along with decreased oxidative stress and markers of inflammation. Decreased recruitment of pro-inflammatory macrophages as measured by RT-qPCR was also observed. In addition, after bariatric surgery, we found lower plasma levels of molecules produced by senescent cells and related to cardiovascular risk including soluble E-selectin (31.3+/-14.0 ng/ml vs. 22.6+/-11.4 ng/ml, p=0.03), ICAM-1 (387.4+/-98.7 ng/ml vs. 338.6 vs. 92.5 ng/ml, p=0.04) and Galectin 3 (12.6+/-8.6 ng/ml vs. 10.0+/-4.9 ng/ml, p=0.12) as well as decreased plasma levels of ACE2 (1.6+/-1.9 ng/ml vs. 0.8+/-1.4 ng/ml, p=0.04). Importantly, we observed decreased expression of ADAM17 in SAT, which plays a crucial role production of a soluble form of ACE2, currently representing a new predictor of cardiovascular damage.

Conclusions: Bariatric surgery reduces the amount of senescent cells in adipose tissue along with attenuation of inflammation and oxidative stress in fat and decreased circulating levels of markers of cardiovascular risk produced by senescent cells. These changes could contribute to the improvement of inflammation and metabolic parameters in patients with obesity along with reduced risk of cardiovascular complications.

GC4.077

Bariatric surgery: Does it improve pain or opioid use?

Kastanias, P.; Wang, W.

University Health Network, Toronto Western Hospital; Lawrence Bloomberg Faculty of Nursing, University of Toronto

Introduction: Bariatric surgery is a well studied, successful and durable treatment for obesity and has become increasingly common. It is well documented that suboptimal post-surgical pain management may lead to chronic pain. However, very few studies examine pain trends after bariatric surgery.

Purpose: This longitudinal, correlational study was designed to examine acute & chronic pain and opioid trends post bariatric surgery.

Methods: Fifty-eight bariatric surgery subjects who underwent either laparoscopic gastric bypass or sleeve gastrectomy at one surgical centre were followed longitudinally. Data was collected at seven time points from preoperatively to 6 months postoperatively.

Results: Average acute postoperative pain severity was moderate immediately following surgery and generally decreased over time. However, there was an increase in acute pain 24hrs after discharge. There was no correlation between acute pain severity and the amount of opioid administered while in hospital. Opioid usage was significantly less at 1-month post-op compared to 48-hours post-discharge (p < 0.01).

At 6 months post-op, the incidence of chronic pain was significantly reduced (p = 0.031), with pain interference in life activities also significantly improved (p < 0.01). No significant difference was found in pain interference in sleep following surgery.

Conclusion: Acute pain appears to be reasonably well controlled following laparoscopic bariatric surgery. Clinicians should be aware that postop pain may spike at discharge & incorporate this into discharge planning and education. Chronic pain and pain interference were both improved at 6 months postoperatively. This study supports the evidence from other longitudinal studies that opioid use initially decreases following bariatric surgery. However more research is needed to examine long term opioid use among bariatric patients who are chronic opioid users.

GC4.078

Ontario Bariatric Network (OBN) and Project ECHO - working towards excellence in obesity care in Ontario, Canada

Kastanias, P.; Wang, W.

University Health Network, Toronto Western Hospital; Lawrence Bloomberg Faculty of Nursing, University of Toronto

With the rise of obesity across the world and its recognition as a chronic illness by the World Health Organisation (WHO), access to excellent, evidence based obesity care has become increasingly important. As a first step to this, building capacity among primary providers is critical.

This presentation will describe: a) medical and surgical obesity treatment options available through the Ontario Bariatric Network (OBN) Centers of Excellence, and b) Project ECHO: an educational model which uses telemedicine technology to improve access to obesity care and share best practices to build capacity among primary care providers through practice based learning.

The Ontario Bariatric Network is a centralised, collaborative network consisting of 11 Bariatric Centers of Excellence across Ontario, Canada. Each centre provides comprehensive, interdisciplinary medical and surgical bariatric services.

Project ECHO is an interdisciplinary, case-based 'Hub & Spoke' model that connects healthcare professionals from Bariatric Centers of Excellence to community providers across the province to provide educational support and clinical consultation expertise at their fingertips through videoconferencing. The 'Hub' is the Ontario Bariatric Centres of Excellence interdisciplinary team. The "Spokes" are the community providers across the province. Each session includes a didactic, evidence based presentation followed by specialty consultation for real cases brought by the community providers. Written recommendations are provided for each case. This model seeks to build capacity for excellence in obesity care.

Both of these programs are fully funded by the Ontario Ministry of Health and offered at no cost to Ontario resident and community participants.

GC4.079

Supporting ethnically diverse populations within a national diabetes intervention; a qualitative evaluation of the experiences of coaches delivering the NHS Low Calorie Diet Programme Pilot

Dhir, P.¹; Maynard, M.¹; Drew, K. J.¹; Homer, C.²; Bakhai, C.³; Ellis, L.¹

¹Obesity Institute, School of Health, Leeds Beckett University, Leeds, LS1 3HB, UK

²Sport and Physical Activity Research Centre, Sheffield Hallam University, Olympic Legacy Park, 2 Old Hall Road, Sheffield S9 3TU, UK

³NHS Bedfordshire, Luton and Milton Keynes Integrated Care Board, Arndale House, Luton, LU1 2LJ

Background: The management of type 2 diabetes within diverse ethnic populations requires a culturally tailored approach. However, little is known about the experiences of coaches delivering interventions for type 2 diabetes (T2D), such as the NHS Low Calorie Diet (LCD) Programme, to people with diverse ethnic backgrounds. T2D disproportionately affects certain ethnic groups such as South Asian and Black ethnicities, with age-standardised prevalence of 13%, 20% and 15% in people of Indian, Pakistani or Bangladeshi ethnicity respectively, and 14% and 11% in people of Black Caribbean and Black African ethnicity respectively. Understanding the challenges, successes, and nuances faced by coaches delivering interventions is paramount for shaping tailored healthcare strategies and reducing health inequalities.

Aims: The aim of this paper is to explore the experiences of health coaches in delivering the programme to ethnically diverse populations to ensure equitable and culturally tailored care. Given the disproportionate impact of T2D on certain ethnic groups, the study aims to bridge the significant knowledge gap regarding the challenges, successes, and nuances faced by coaches in culturally tailored diabetes management interventions, in order to inform future service development.